

Comparison of K-Eigenvalue Iteration Methods for Neutron Diffusion Equation

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ABSTRACT

The neutron diffusion equation is discretized into a generalized eigenvalue problem using the continuous Finite Element Method (FEM). It was solved using traditional power iteration method and eigenvalue iterative algorithms based on Krylov subspace ideas, including Krylov schur method, generalized Davidson method, and Jacobi Davidson method. Firstly, the number of iterations and computation time of the power iteration method and Krylov based iteration algorithm were compared. Then, the preconditioning techniques of Krylov based iterative methods were studied. Through the calculation of the IAEA 3D benchmark problem, the results show that the Davidson type iterative algorithm combined with incomplete LU decomposition preconditioning technology has highest computational efficiency. For a problem with two million elements, the calculation can be completed within one minute by using a single core, compared with the traditional power iteration methods, the computational efficiency is improved by about 18 times.

Keywords: Neutron Diffusion Equation, Finite Element Method, Krylov Subspace Method, Davidson Method

1. INTRODUCTION

The neutron diffusion equation is a low-order approximation of the neutron transport equation, it is commonly used in the core calculation of the two-step calculation framework. Due to its high computational efficiency and accuracy to meet the engineering design requirements, it is widely used in practical engineering applications such as critical search, fuel management, and transient calculation. There are many mature numerical methods that can be used to solve the neutron diffusion equation, including the finite difference method, the nodal method, the finite element method, etc. Considering that some new type reactors have the characteristics of irregular geometric

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structures, this paper uses the finite element method to discretize the space, which is suitable for any unstructured geometry.

The numerical solution of the neutron diffusion equation mainly includes the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}) and the neutron flux density, which correspond to the maximum eigenvalue and eigenvector of the generalized eigenvalue problem. At present, the power iteration method is widely used to solve the effective multiplication factor, since its number of iterations depends on the dominance ratio of the problem (the ratio of the second largest and the largest eigenvalues), the closer the dominance ratio is to 1, the more iterations will be required. In actual PWR, the dominance ratio is generally close to 1, resulting in slow convergence of the power iteration method. For the generalized eigenvalue problem, many efficient solution methods have been developed[1], including Krylov-Schur method, generalized Davidson method[2], and Jacobi-Davidson method[3], etc. Most of these methods are based on the idea of Krylov subspace, it project the original problem onto the Krylov subspace, and approximating the eigenvalue and eigenvector by solving a reduced order problem. These methods can also be accelerated through preconditioning techniques[4]. The Jacobi preconditioning (JACOBI), incomplete LU decomposition preconditioning (ILU), and algebraic multigrid preconditioning (AMG) are studied in this paper.

The finite element solution of the neutron diffusion equation program is developed by using the open source finite element library libMesh[5]. Firstly, the power iteration method is used to solve the eigenvalues. Then, with the help of the SLEPc[6] and PETSc[7] solver, the Krylov-Schur method, the generalized Davidson method, and the Jacobi-Davidson method are used to solve the eigenvalues, and the Jacobi preconditioning, the incomplete LU decomposition preconditioning, and the algebraic multigrid preconditioning are studied. Finally, through the calculation of the IAEA 3D benchmark problem, the number of iterations and the computation time of various methods are compared.

2. Methods

2.1. Neutron Diffusion Equation and Finite Element Discretization

Neutron Diffusion Equation:The multi-group neutron diffusion equation and its boundary conditions are given by:

$$-\nabla D_g \nabla \phi_g + \Sigma_{t,g} \phi_g - \sum_{g'=1}^G \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \phi_{g'} = \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu \Sigma_{f,g'} \phi_{g'}, \mathbf{r} \in \Omega, g = 1, \dots, G \quad (1)$$

$$D_g \mathbf{n} \cdot \nabla \phi_g + \frac{1}{2} \frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta} \phi_g = 0, \mathbf{r} \in \partial\Omega \quad (2)$$

Weak Form:Using the weighted residual method: 1) Multiply Eq. (1) by weighting function w and integrate over space; 2) Apply integration by parts to the leakage term; 3) Substitute boundary condition. This yields the weak form:

$$\frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta} w \phi_g \, d\mathbf{r} + \int_{\Omega} D_g \nabla w \nabla \phi_g + \Sigma_{t,g} w \phi_g \, d\mathbf{r} - \sum_{g'=1}^G \int_{\Omega} \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} w \phi_{g'} \, d\mathbf{r} = \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \sum_{g'=1}^G \int_{\Omega} \nu \Sigma_{f,g'} w \phi_{g'} \, d\mathbf{r} \quad (3)$$

Finite Element Discretization: Using Galerkin FEM with basis functions $\{\varphi_j, j=1, \dots, N\}$ for flux expansion and selecting basis functions as weighting functions gives the semi-discrete form:

$$\sum_{j=1}^N \phi_{g,j} \left(\begin{array}{l} \frac{1}{2} \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{1-\beta}{1+\beta} \varphi_i \varphi_j d\mathbf{r} \\ + \int_{\Omega} D_g \nabla \varphi_i \nabla \varphi_j d\mathbf{r} \\ + \int_{\Omega} \Sigma_{t,g} \varphi_i \varphi_j d\mathbf{r} \end{array} \right) - \sum_{j=1}^N \sum_{g'=1}^G \phi_{g',j} \int_{\Omega} \Sigma_{s,g' \rightarrow g} \varphi_i \varphi_j d\mathbf{r} = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}} \chi_g \sum_{g'=1}^G \sum_{j=1}^N \phi_{g',j} \int_{\Omega} \nu \Sigma_{f,g'} \varphi_i \varphi_j d\mathbf{r} \quad (4)$$

The above equation can be rearranged into matrix form as follows:

$$\mathbf{L}\phi = \frac{1}{k_{\text{eff}}}\mathbf{F}\phi \quad (5)$$

This constitutes a generalized eigenvalue problem, whose solution provides: the dominant eigenvalue k_{eff} (effective multiplication factor) and the corresponding eigenvector ϕ (neutron flux distribution).

2.2. Solve with Iterative method

Power Iteration method: The power iteration method is usually used to solve Eq. (5). The algorithm is as follows:

- step 1: Initialize: $k_{\text{eff}}^{(0)} = k_{\text{eff}}^0, \phi^{(0)} = \phi^0$
 step 2: Solve the flux distribution: $\phi^{(n)} = \mathbf{L}^{-1}\mathbf{F}\phi^{(n-1)} / k_{\text{eff}}^{(n-1)}$
 step 3: Update the effective multiplication factor: $k_{\text{eff}}^{(n)} = k_{\text{eff}}^{(n-1)} \frac{|\mathbf{F}\phi^{(n)}|}{|\mathbf{F}\phi^{(n-1)}|}$
 step 4: Check converges: $\left| \frac{k_{\text{eff}}^{(n)} - k_{\text{eff}}^{(n-1)}}{k_{\text{eff}}^{(n)}} \right| < \varepsilon_k, \left| \frac{\phi^{(n)} - \phi^{(n-1)}}{\phi^{(n)}} \right| < \varepsilon_\phi$
 step 5: If not converges, return to step 2

It can be seen that $|\mathbf{F}\phi| / k_{\text{eff}}$ remains unchanged during the iteration. Because the neutron flux is an eigenvector, its absolute magnitude can be arbitrarily scaled, meaning the total fission source $|\mathbf{F}\phi| / k_{\text{eff}}$ can be any constant.

Fission Source Normalization: The total fission source can be normalized, which results in

$$k_{\text{eff}} = |\mathbf{F}\phi| \quad (6)$$

Generally, the effective multiplication factor is close to 1, therefore, for the fission source normalization, initialization can be performed in the following ways:

$$k_{\text{eff}}^{(0)} = 1, \phi^{(0)} = \phi^0 / |\mathbf{F}\phi^0| \quad (7)$$

Thus, the fission source normalized power iteration algorithm is as follows:

- step 1: Initialize: $k_{\text{eff}}^{(0)} = 1, \phi^{(0)} = \phi^0 / |\mathbf{F}\phi^0|$
 step 2: Solve the flux distribution: $\phi^{(n)} = \mathbf{L}^{-1}\mathbf{F}\phi^{(n-1)} / k_{\text{eff}}^{(n-1)}$
 step 3: Update the effective multiplication factor: $k_{\text{eff}}^{(n)} = |\mathbf{F}\phi^{(n)}|$
 step 4: Check converges: $\left| \frac{k_{\text{eff}}^{(n)} - k_{\text{eff}}^{(n-1)}}{k_{\text{eff}}^{(n)}} \right| < \varepsilon_k, \left| \frac{\phi^{(n)} - \phi^{(n-1)}}{\phi^{(n)}} \right| < \varepsilon_\phi$
 step 5: If not converges, return to step 2

This process can simplify the iterative process and if a nonlinear solver, such as the JFNK method[8], is used to solve Eq. (5), using Eq. (6) and Eq. (7) can avoid introducing additional equations.

Krylov Subspace Method:For the eigenvalue problem of a large-scale sparse matrix,

$$\mathbf{Ax} = \lambda \mathbf{x} \quad (9)$$

The power iteration method only iterates on one vector at a time, while the Krylov subspace method constructs a series of subspaces with increasing dimensions and then approximately solves the eigenvalue and eigenvector of the original problem by projecting it to the low-dimensional subspace.

The algorithm is as follows:

step 1: Initialize: Choose a random starting vector \mathbf{v}_1 with $\|\mathbf{v}_1\| = 1$, Set the subspace dimension m .

step 2: Arnoldi process: Build an orthonormal basis $\mathbf{V}_m = [\mathbf{v}_1, \mathbf{v}_2, \dots, \mathbf{v}_m]$ with Arnoldi Decomposition $\mathbf{AV}_m = \mathbf{V}_m \mathbf{H}_m + f_m \mathbf{e}_m^T$.

Step 3: Projection: Project to the subspace $\mathbf{H}_m = \mathbf{V}_m^T \mathbf{AV}_m$, Solve the small eigenvalue problem $\mathbf{H}_m \mathbf{y} = \theta \mathbf{y}$ to obtain the Ritz pairs (θ, \mathbf{x}) , $\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{V}_m \mathbf{y}$.

step 4: Check Convergence: $\mathbf{r} = \mathbf{Ax} - \theta \mathbf{x}$, $\|\mathbf{r}\|_2 < \varepsilon$.

step 5: Restart: If not converged, Select new starting vector, return to step 2.

The Krylov subspace can be constructed through the Arnoldi process. Combined with restart and preconditioning techniques, many iterative algorithms based on the Krylov subspace idea have been developed, such as Krylov-Schur method, Generalized Davidson method, Jacobi-Davidson method, etc.

Krylov-Schur method: Implicitly restarting the process with Schur decomposition, selectively retaining dominant subspace directions while maintaining numerical stability. The Krylov-Schur restart strategy is as follows:

KS step 1: After m Arnoldi steps, compute $\mathbf{H}_m = \mathbf{QTQ}^H$ (Schur decomp).

KS step 2: Reorder \mathbf{T} to group desired eigenvalues $(\theta_1, \dots, \theta_k)$.

KS step 3: Keep first k Schur vectors: $\mathbf{V}_k = \mathbf{V}_m \mathbf{Q}_{1:k}$, $\mathbf{H}_k = \mathbf{T}_{1:k,1:k}$.

KS step 4: Continue Arnoldi with \mathbf{V}_k as new basis.

Generalized Davidson method: Correct the subspace using preconditioning method. At each iteration, generate a new direction via preconditioned residual as follows:

GD step 1: Solve correction equation approximately: $(\mathbf{A} - \theta \mathbf{I})\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{r}$, by using a few iterations of preconditioned iterative solver (e.g., GMRES with ILU preconditioning).

GD step 2: Orthogonalization against current basis: $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{t} - \mathbf{V}(\mathbf{V}^T \mathbf{t})$;

GD step 3: Expand subspace: $\mathbf{V} = [\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{t} / \|\mathbf{t}\|]$.

Jacobi-Davidson method: Projects and solves a corrected equation to expand the subspace as follows:

JD step 1 : Solve correction equation approximately: $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}^T)(\mathbf{A} - \theta\mathbf{I})(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}^T)\mathbf{t} = -\mathbf{r}$, where the vector \mathbf{x} is the current approximation to the desired eigenvector, obtained from a Ritz pair .

JD step 2: Orthogonalization against current basis: $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{t} - \mathbf{V}(\mathbf{V}^T\mathbf{t})$;

JD step 3: Expand subspace: $\mathbf{V} = [\mathbf{V}, \mathbf{t} / \|\mathbf{t}\|]$.

3. Results and Discussion

Based on the theoretical model above, this paper develops a finite element solver for the neutron diffusion equation rely on the C++ open-source library libMesh[5]. By computing the IAEA 3D benchmark problem, different eigenvalue iteration methods are compared.

3.1. Verification Results

The benchmark problem involves a 3D two-group PWR model from Argonne National Laboratory, featuring 177 fuel assemblies comparable to commercial PWRs [10]. The finite element method is used to solve this problem, Using ~2.03 million tetrahedral elements with a convergence criterion of 1.0E-5 for flux and keff. The calculation result of the effective multiplication factor is 1.02981 (reference:1.02903), with a 78 pcm deviation. The flux distribution results are shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Flux Distribution Results

3.2. Performance Comparison without Preconditioning

Table 1 presents the performance comparison of different iterative methods using a single core (Intel(R) Xeon(R) Gold 6326 CPU @ 2.90GHz) without acceleration or preconditioning. Results demonstrate that Krylov-Schur requires the fewest iterations, while generalized Davidson needs the most. Jacobi-Davidson achieves the fastest computation time, being 10 times more efficient than

power iteration (versus 5 times for Krylov-Schur). Fig. 2 confirms that despite Krylov-Schur's iteration advantage, Davidson methods show superior efficiency for neutron diffusion problems, with generalized Davidson maintaining comparable performance to Jacobi-Davidson despite requiring more iterations.

Table.1.Comparison of Iterative Methods without Preconditioning

Method	Outer Iteration Number	Computation Time/s
Power Iteration Method (Fission Source Normalization)	93	980.4
Krylov-Schur Method	4	290.4
GeneralizedDavidson Method	390	108.2
Jacobi-Davidson Method	14	100.5

Fig. 2.Convergence Process of Different Iterative Methods

3.3. Performance Comparison with Preconditioning

For the iterative algorithm based on the Krylov subspace idea, preconditioning can be used to improve the computational efficiency. This paper compares the computation time and the number of iterations of several preconditioning methods, including Jacobi preconditioning (JACOBI), Incomplete LU Decomposition preconditioning (ILU(0) is adopted which preserves only the non-zero sparsity pattern of the original matrix, offering a memory-efficient and widely used preconditioner for general sparse linear systems.)[4], and Algebraic Multigrid preconditioning (AMG is a highly scalable preconditioner that automatically constructs a hierarchy of coarse-level problems from the matrix algebraically, making it particularly effective for elliptic-type operators such as those in neutron diffusion equations.))[11]. The number of iterations is compared in Fig. 3a, and the computation time is compared in Fig. 3b. The results show that the preconditioning techniques have little effect on the iteration number of Krylov Schur and Jacobi Davidson methods, but can significantly reduce the

iteration number of the generalized Davidson method. All of these preconditioning techniques can improve the computational efficiency of Krylov based iterative methods. Overall, incomplete LU decomposition preconditioning has the highest computational efficiency, it can accelerate the Krylov based method by approximately 2.5 times.

Fig. 3. Performance Comparison with Preconditioning

4. Conclusion

This paper investigates efficient iterative methods for computing the dominant eigenvalue (k_{eff}) of the neutron diffusion equation. We introduce a fission source-normalized power iteration to simplify updates and enable nonlinear iteration, and compare advanced eigensolvers—Krylov–Schur, Generalized Davidson, and Jacobi–Davidson, finding that while Krylov–Schur minimizes iteration count, Jacobi–Davidson achieves the shortest runtime. Among preconditioners (Jacobi, ILU(0), and AMG), ILU(0) offers the best trade-off for large-scale problems. On a 2-million-cell mesh, Jacobi–Davidson with ILU(0) solves the eigenproblem in under one minute on a single core—delivering an $18\times$ speedup over traditional power iteration.

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References

- [1] Gene H. Golub, Charles F. Van Loan, Matrix Computation (4th Edition), People's Post and Telecommunication Press: Beijing, 2020.

- [2] Wenbo Zhao, Xiaoming Chai, Bin Zhang, Jiayi Liu, Xingjie Peng, Tianya Li, Junchong Yu, A nodal method based on CMFD for pin-by-pin SP3 calculation, *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, Volume 167, 2022, 108849
- [3] E. Romero and J.E. Roman, "A Parallel Implementation of Davidson Methods for Large-Scale Eigenvalue Problems in SLEPc", *ACM Trans. Math. Software* 40(2):13, 2014.
- [4] Saad, Y. (2003). *Iterative Methods for Sparse Linear Systems* (2nd ed.). SIAM (Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics). Chapter 10: Preconditioning Techniques, pp. 267–334.
- [5] Kirk BS, Peterson JW, Stogner RH, et al. libMesh: a C++ library for parallel adaptive mesh refinement/coarsening simulations[J]. *Engineering with Computers*, 2006, 22(3): 237-254.
- [6] E. Roman, C. Campos, E. Romero, A. Tomas, SLEPc Users Manual, Tech. Rep. DSIC-II/24/02 – Revision 3.12, Universitat of Politecnica de Valencia ,2019.
- [7] S. Balay, S. Abhyankar, M. Adams and et al, PETSc Users manual, Tech. Rep. ANL-95/11 – Revision 3.8, Argonne National Laboratory (2017).
- [8] Li Zhigang, An Ping, He Tao, et al. Research on JFNK Method Based on Neutron Diffusion Equation[J]. *Nuclear Power Engineering*, Vol 40.S2:0067,2019.
- [9] Dai Xiaoying, Gao Xingyu. The Davidson Type Method for Eigenvalue Problems and Its Implementation Techniques[J]. *Numerical Computation and Computer Applications*.2006.9.3
- [10] Argonne Code Center. Benchmark Problem Book[R]. ANL-7416. Computational Benchmark Problems Committee of the Mathematics and Computation Division of the American Nuclear Society, 1977.
- [11] Falgout, R. D. (2006). An introduction to algebraic multigrid. *Computing in Science & Engineering*, 8(6), 24–33.